



Welcome to the third issue of the Harpoocrates Newsletter!

We've prepared a lot of exciting updates and insights for you, from publications to inspiring conference highlights and our new podcast series.



Silence and Security: Harpoocrates' Legacy in Healthcare Innovation

In the annals of history, there's an intriguing tale about the Greek god Harpoocrates, symbolizing silence and secrets...

Learn More



GuardML: Efficient Privacy-Preserving Machine Learning - Tampere University

We're sharing TUNI's latest publication on privacy-preserving machine learning. Congrats to authors Eugene Frimpong, Khoa Nguyen, Mindaugas Budzys, Tanveer Khan, and Antonis Michalakis!

Learn More



University of Eastern Finland (UEF) Leading the Way in Harpoocrates Project: Data Sharing and analysis for social utility

Sami Nikkonen, representing the University of Eastern Finland (UEF), delivered a 15-minute presentation on the HARPOCRATES project during the Musculoskeletal Diseases Research Community Seminar Series...

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Vladimir Radomirovic, from Zentrix Lab Introduces Harpoocrates at Web Summit 2023 - Lisbon, Portugal

Vladimir Radomirovic, representing Zentrix Lab doo, took part in the WEBSUMMIT 2023 conference held in Lisbon, Portugal from November 11 to November 14th 2023.

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Interview with Roberto Sandrini from Region Veneto: 'Insights from a HARPOCRATES Threat Intelligence Demonstrator'.

In this interview, we talk with Roberto Sandrini from Veneto Region, Italy, one of the HARPOCRATES Threat Intelligence Demonstrators. We'll explore their part in boosting cybersecurity and how Harpoocrates addresses challenges in public administration cybersecurity.

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Exploring Cybersecurity Innovations: An Interview with Ricardo Gonçalves, HARPOCRATES Project Focus Group Member

In our latest feature, we dive into the world of cybersecurity innovations with Ricardo Gonçalves, a valued member of the HARPOCRATES project focus group. Ricardo shares his insights on the current state of cybersecurity, the challenges faced in protecting sensitive data, and how the HARPOCRATES project is addressing these issues.

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HARPOCRATES Podcast

Introducing our new podcast series, Harpoocrates Chats! We explore tech innovation and personal privacy, perfect for the tech-savvy and privacy-conscious.

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HARPOCRATES Consortium Recap in Saariselkä, Lapland

Discover key insights from the recent HARPOCRATES Consortium gathering in Saariselkä, Lapland. The event focused on advancing privacy solutions, with participants discussing groundbreaking approaches to data security and confidentiality.

Learn More



Explore the HARPOCRATES Network

Discover the extensive network behind the HARPOCRATES project. Our collaborative efforts bring together experts and organizations dedicated to advancing privacy and security in healthcare and beyond.

Explore the Network



Advancing Privacy-Preserving Neural Network Training: Insights from the Harpoocrates Project at PETS Conference

Discover the HARPOCRATES project's latest paper, 'Wilded Dreams: Reproducible Research in Privacy-preserving Neural Network Training,' and unlock insights into innovative privacy-preserving techniques.

Read full paper

Enhancing Fairness in Blockchain Data Exchanges: Insights from Tampere University at SACMAT Conference

Discover Tampere University's 'FEI]Chain,' advancing fair blockchain data exchanges with a new encryption scheme. Congratulations to Camille Nuoskaia, Reyhaneh Rabbannejad, Antonis Michalakis, and Tassos Dimitriou on their impactful research at SACMAT.

Read full paper



The Harpoocrates consortium is made up of 13 partners from 9 countries, including prestigious universities, research institutes, SMEs, and government bodies.

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STAY TUNED!

Stay updated on all our latest news, developments, research and general information regarding the HARPOCRATES project.



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